

Workshop Recommendation from Customer Feedback Using Sentiment Analysis

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Abstract—OnRoad vehicle breakdown assistance finders help find the nearest mechanic shop that let them book services for their vehicle work. But in this process of choosing nearby mechanic shops, they're unaware of the fact whether the shops they go actually provide best services or not and in order to know they have to conduct verbal conversations with people for reviews which is technically not a feasible option. Here comes the potential need for a strong recommendations system that generates feedback based on user reviews through sentiment analyses that let them choose the right workshop. The systematic identification of emotions such as positivity, negativity, or neutrality in textual data is involved in sentiment analysis, which is also known as opinion mining. Subjective data is extracted and analyzed using text analysis and NLP in this technique, which finds applications in a variety of fields such as marketing, customer service, and clinical medicine. The analysis of service-based feedback in the paper focuses on determining users' level of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the mechanic service by analyzing their emotions. It is possible to quickly identify the emotional state of customers and the factors that contribute to it by evaluating their feedback.

Hybrid approach which is a combination of lexicon approach and TextBlob approach using Naïve Bayes algorithm. TextBlob approach helps in identifying misspelled words and providing potential solutions is the process of correcting them in a text. In a document, a Spell Checker tool is usually utilized to identify misspelled words. The program Spell Checker scans the dictionary to identify words spelled incorrectly and proposes replacements.

Keywords: Sentiment Analysis, TextBlob, Flask, Lexicon, Spelling Correction, Naive Bayes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Onroad vehicle breakdown assistance finder project is to connect drivers with nearby workshops in case of vehicle breakdowns. Drivers can search for assistance services and request help in case of a breakdown using the platform's user-friendly interface. Based on the driver's location, type of vehicle, and required services, the project provides a workshop recommendation system that suggests the most suitable workshop.

Using sentiment analysis, the workshop recommendation system utilizes customer feedback to determine the emotions and opinions expressed in customer reviews. This helps users let decide them decide to chose their service or not based on user reviews. The system can identify the workshops that are most likely to provide high-quality services and meet the needs and preferences of drivers by analyzing customer feedback. The system utilizes sentiment analysis to extract

useful insights from the large number of customer reviews available online. These insights are then used to offer personalized recommendations to drivers. Here we have used a hybrid approach that comprises both lexicon approach and TextBlob approach. Lexcion approach for semantic analyses which is a technique that calculates the semantic orientations of the data given which could be in document format or set of sentences from semantic orientations of lexicons. Semantic orientation can be positive, negative or neutral through which a conclusion is generated after analyzing the input data. TextBlob approach helps in identifying misspelled spellings that helps in producing only accurate results.

The Onroad vehicle breakdown assistance finder project uses sentimental analysis of customer feedback to recommend workshops to mechanics. This innovative platform enhances the efficiency of mechanic services and provides a better experience to drivers who encounter vehicle breakdowns. By utilizing sentiment analysis, the project identifies areas for improvement in mechanic services and offers personalized recommendations to drivers, resulting in improved customer satisfaction and loyalty.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Fang et al.[1], The concept of sentiment analysis is introduced, which studies people's opinions towards entities, especially through online data. The potential and limitations of online data sources are discussed, highlighting the lack of quality control and ground truth. The main emphasis of the paper is on categorizing the polarity of sentiments by suggesting techniques for detecting negation phrases, calculating sentiment scores, and producing feature vectors. The performance of classification models is evaluated in the paper through experiments on sentence and review-level categorization..

According to Drus et al.[2], Provides an overview of related literature published between 2014 to 2019 and discusses the use of sentiment analysis in social media. Using Natural Language Processing (NLP), sentiment analysis extracts opinions from text and categorizes them as positive, negative, or neutral. Sentiment analysis has been employed in business and marketing, politics and public action context, and has been extended to languages other than English, as indicated by the study. Emphasizing the significance of social media in sentiment analysis studies due to its vast amount of data from online users.

According to Mishra et al.[3], Use of non-English languages

for sentiment analysis is one of the main issues with natural language processing. In this paper, we describe a simple but efficient approach that delivers precise findings when immediately analysing the sentiment of the comments in non-English languages.

According to G. S. N. Murthy et al.[4], This article explains the utilization of rating predictions in social media to anticipate product ratings by analyzing user reviews. A new model, called social sentiment influence, is introduced in the article. This model consolidates the user's own sentimental attribute with the previous factors in the recommender system. Using certain keywords, the average rating of the product is to be predicted. The article examines different methodologies, such as matrix factorization, applications based on reviews, and applications based on sentiment. Efficient products can now be predicted with the addition of features such as poor, bad, and wonderful.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Customer feedback emotions can be detected using other approaches such as analyzing customer reviews. This involves performing a word check and only considering words with correct spellings to ensure accuracy. Words with incorrect spellings are not counted as positive or negative, but are instead considered neutral. A common problem faced by most models is accuracy issues caused by spelling mistakes and other factors. This paper presents a user-friendly web application form that can easily detect and solve spelling mistakes.

1. Preprocessing Methods

The feedbacks stored in database will be preprocessed, including steps such as spell checking to count correct spellings and disregard incorrect ones, followed by neutral feedback, stemming, lowercase conversion, stop word removal, and tokenization. Breaking the text into meaningful components or tokens, such as words or phrases, is what tokenization involves. Also, conjunctions and prepositions, which are stop words frequently used in texts but not related to a specific subject, will be removed. Before the classification stages, all uppercase letters will be converted to lowercase as an additional step. To determine the stem or root of derived words is the final step in the preprocessing procedure.

2. Feature extraction

The process of converting input data into a set of features is known as feature extraction. The performance of the machine learning process is substantially impacted by choosing the right set of features. To help the classifier, the input data is converted and summarized into a set of characteristic features, or feature vectors.

3. Text Classification

Naive base is used in this experiment.

A machine learning model, the Naive Bayes classifier, has been trained on a large corpus of workshop reviews to perform sentiment analysis. A commonly used probabilistic machine learning algorithm for text classification tasks is Naive Bayes, on which the model is based.

The Naive Bayes algorithm for sentiment analysis calculates the probability of a given text belonging to one of three sentiment categories (positive, negative, or neutral) by

analyzing the frequency of specific words and phrases in the text. A labeled dataset of workshop reviews was used to train the model, with each review being classified as either positive or negative. The model associates certain words and phrases with positive or negative sentiment during training, based on their frequency in positive and negative reviews.

4. Overall Design

To effectively recognize customer emotions, a sentiment analysis system is being developed in this paper. A hybrid approach, combining TextBlob and a lexicon-based approach, was utilized to construct the system. Python module TextBlob provides natural language processing features like sentiment analysis and spelling correction. TextBlob's spelling correction feature was utilized to enhance the precision of the sentiment analysis outcomes. Based on sentiment, feedback is classified as positive, negative, or neutral using the Naive Bayes algorithm in the system. Flask, a Python web framework, was utilized to develop a user-friendly interface for the system in addition. The system can accurately recognize customer emotions by analyzing vast amounts of feedback data with this hybrid approach.

The software & libraries for the Sentiment analysis system are:

- Python (3.10.4)
- Flask (1.0.2)
- TextBlob
- Lexicon
- NLTK

5. Techniques Used

(i) Naive Base:

Naive Bayes is a probabilistic machine learning algorithm commonly used for text classification tasks such as sentiment analysis. It is a simple but powerful algorithm that can achieve high accuracy with relatively little training data.

Hybrid approach has been used which involves Lexicon approach and TextBlob for pre-trained Naive Bayes classifier for sentiment analysis, the algorithm works by calculating the probability of a given text belonging to each of the three sentiment categories (positive, negative, or neutral) based on the frequency of certain words and phrases in the text. The classifier has been trained on a large corpus of workshop reviews, where each review is labeled as either positive or negative. During training, TextBlob is used for spelling correction to generate accurate results and also the classifier learns to associate certain words and phrases with positive or negative sentiment based on the frequency of these words in the positive and negative reviews.

Once the classifier is trained, it can be used to classify new text as positive, negative, or neutral based on the presence of certain words and phrases. The classifier calculates the probability of the text belonging to each of the three categories based on the frequency of these words and phrases, and then assigns the text to the category with the highest probability.

The term 'Naive' in Naive Bayes denotes the assumption that every feature, such as each word or phrase in the text, is

independent of all other features. The calculations are simplified and the algorithm can handle a large number of features, even with limited training data, thanks to this assumption. Although Naive Bayes makes a naive assumption and is simple, it is a powerful algorithm that can achieve high accuracy in many text classification tasks.

TextBlob's pre-trained Naive Bayes classifier for sentiment analysis has achieved high accuracy on various sentiment analysis benchmarks, making it a popular choice for sentiment analysis tasks. However, it is important to note that the accuracy of the classifier may vary depending on the domain and context of the text being analyzed, and that it may not always be the best choice for all sentiment analysis tasks.

One technique for calculating the semantic orientations of data, which may be in document format or a set of sentences, is the lexicon-based approach for semantic analysis. After analyzing the input data, a conclusion is generated based on its positive, negative, or neutral semantic orientation..

IV. RESULTS

To analyze user feedback and determine whether it is positive or negative, the study you described aims to use natural language processing (NLP) techniques for predicting emotions from text data. Based on the feedback received, the proposed system uses this analysis to generate a rating for the product.

The system can identify the workshops that are most highly rated by customers for the services they provide by analyzing customer feedback in this manner. The system may suggest nearby workshops or highlight it on the website as the most reviewed workshop if a specific workshop consistently receives positive feedback, to other customers in remote locations.

Processing large amounts of text data and extracting useful insights from it can be effectively achieved by using NLP in this context. It is worth noting that NLP techniques are not always 100% accurate and can sometimes produce false positives or false negatives. Before using the system to inform business decisions, it is important to carefully evaluate its performance and consider any potential limitations or biases in the data.

To determine the sentiment score of textual feedback, use the following examples as an explanation.

1) Example Feedback1: Your workshop provides excellent service

Positive Word : excellent
score is $1-0 = 1$ (Positive).

2) Example Feedback2: The Service is Very Bad.

Negative words: Bad
Positive words: No positive words
Score: $1-0 = -1$ (Negative)

Fig 1: Workflow of the system

Fig 3 : Postive Feedback Updated

ws_id	users_id	ws_name	username	place	address	licenseum	email	phone	isApproved	status	count	lat	lon	neg	neu
1	4	ABCD	abcd	Kottayam	ABC Workshop	0987654321	arunbabu2022a@mca.ac.in	9076543222	1	1	0	9.590230	76.016653	0	0
2	5	On Wheels	onwheels	Mundakayam	On Wheels Workshop	1987650100	ahm@ahm2010@gmail.com	9076543211	1	1	29	9.537060	76.084773	10	6
5	15	Maruthii	Maruthi	Kottayam	Maruthi Workshop	2098073035	ahm@gmail.com	9076543221	1	1	7	9.591967	76.522196	2	1

Fig 4 : Feedback Updated in Database

Fig 5 : Most reviewed Workshop Recommended

V. CONCLUSION

To conclude with, Using sentiment analysis in the on-road breakdown assistance finder project turned out to be successful after implementations. Using sentiment analysis as a powerful tool can assist in gathering insights into customer feedback and levels of satisfaction. The project team can achieve a better understanding of their users' needs and expectations by analyzing the language and tone used in customer reviews. Using this information can enhance the overall functionality of the project, resulting in a better user experience and higher customer satisfaction.

Incorporating sentiment analysis into the on-road breakdown assistance finder project can help the team quickly identify and address any issues or concerns raised by customers. Moreover, it can be beneficial. Improving the overall quality of the service provided can enhance the project's credibility and reputation. The team can make data-driven decisions that benefit both the project and its users by using sentiment analysis to monitor trends and track changes in customer sentiment over time. In general,

incorporating sentiment analysis into the on-road breakdown assistance finder project is a beneficial enhancement that is expected to produce favorable outcomes for everyone.

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